

The Long-Term Effects of Populism on Foreign Policy: Berlusconi's Legacy and Its Impact on Italy's Approach to the EU and International Politics

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Abstract

What are the long-term effects of populism on foreign policy? This aspect has not been addressed yet by the burgeoning literature on the international consequences of populism. In this contribution, we hypothesise that the two distinctive features of populist foreign policy-making, mobilisation/politicisation and personalisation/centralisation, leave a long-term imprint on foreign policy. We carry out a first plausibility probe of our hypotheses by addressing the legacy of Silvio Berlusconi on Italy's foreign policy. To that end, we trace elements of continuity and change in subsequent populist and non-populist governments. We find that the politicisation of foreign policy that was distinctively promoted by Berlusconi has remained a feature of Italian foreign policy across all successive governments. This concerns especially Italy's approach to the European Union and migration policies. Moreover, the personalisation of politics initiated by Berlusconi and the trend towards a strengthening of the Presidency of the Council of Ministers were taken over by successive Italian governments, including by technocratic ones.

Keywords: Berlusconi; foreign policy; Italy; legacy; populism

Introduction

Over the past years, populism has established itself as a political phenomenon across the world, and it has a number of longer term implications. Whilst some populist leaders like Hungarian Prime Minister Orbán in 2010, or more recently US President Trump, were able to make a political comeback, there is growing evidence that populist leaders, even after having been voted out of power, leave a substantial legacy on their countries' democratic institutions and political culture. Populism 'disfigures democracy' (Urbinati, 2019) and contributes to democratic backsliding and political polarisation (Müller, 2016; Pappas, 2019). In the field of economics, research has shown the long-lasting adverse effects of populism in countries like Argentina (Marzetti and Spruk, 2023), and a recent study systematically analysed the economic legacy of populist leaders in terms of long-term GDP per capita losses (Funke et al., 2023).

Whereas these domestic longitudinal effects of populism have become the object of a growing body of research, the longer term consequences of populism in power for a country's foreign policy are still entirely unexplored. This is surprising as populists have at times brought momentous foreign policy change, and we have evidence of non-populist leaders taking over some policies of their populist predecessors, as US President Biden carries on with Trump's protectionist measures against China (Skonieczny and Sherel, 2024). This contribution makes a first step towards filling this gap by asking what

the longer term impact of populism on foreign policy is and by theorising under what conditions populist leaders leave a foreign policy legacy even after being voted out of office.

To address these questions, we proceed as follows. First, we outline the state of the art, tracing the development of studies on the international dimensions of populism and elaborating on our research gap on the foreign policy legacy of populism. We then proceed to theorise how populist leaders can be expected to leave a legacy on their countries' foreign policies, developing expectations around the mechanisms of mobilisation/politicisation and personalisation/centralisation. In the empirical part of the article, we assess the plausibility of those expectations (Eckstein, 1975) by focusing on the case of Italy, assessing the long-term consequences of populism in power since Berlusconi governed repeatedly from the 1990s onwards. Indeed, he was prime minister (officially the President of the Council of Ministers) for 8 months in 1994, nearly 5 years from 2001 to 2006, and three and a half years from 2008 to 2011. From 1994 to 2011, he was either prime minister or leader of the opposition. During this long time, Berlusconi established a post-ideological political party with minimal organisation. By speaking directly to and for the people, denouncing the political elite and the existing party system, Berlusconi could be defined a 'tele-populist' (Tarchi, 2015, p. 295). He represented a form of 'liberal populism' (Orsina, 2014, p. 35) or 'mainstream liberal populism' (Verbeek and Zaslove, 2016, p. 309), identifying the good Italian people as consumers and producers of material goods. Berlusconi as a leader presented himself as a self-made man who knew how to do things, forcefully arguing that people should have trust in his ability to rule. The elite against whom Berlusconi lashed out was that of professional politicians, evoking the populist phenomenon of *L'Uomo qualunque*, and the drawing rooms of Italian capitalism from which he had always been kept out.¹ At times, Berlusconi's anti-elitism entailed attacks against his opponents formulated in impolite language, which polarised Italian politics.

The case of Berlusconi is particularly useful to carry out a plausibility probe of our hypotheses on the long-term effects of populism for several reasons. First, his era was followed by a number of governments with different political orientations. Following Sartori's advice to analyse Italian politics by focusing not on single political parties and frequently changing governments, but rather on larger shifts in the structure of the political system (Sartori, 1976, 1982), we identify three phases in the post-Berlusconi era: (a) the Renzi government (February 2014–December 2016), which reached a 'pivotal central position' (Guidi, 2015, p. 63) in the party system; (b) the Conte I government during the 'populist decade' (Vassallo and Verzichelli, 2023), which started with the 2013 elections, when the populist Five Star Movement was the single most-voted party, and went until the election on 25 September 2022, however entailing only one populist government, the 'yellow-green' coalition of Five Star Movement and League (June 2018–August 2019); and (c) the right-wing Meloni government (from October 2022 until the time of this writing in March 2025), which saw the emergence of a new post-Berlusconian centre-right pole (Chiaramonte and De Sio, 2024). In the following, we will ask whether

¹*Qualunquismo* was a political movement with conservative tendencies that was promoted by the comedian and publicist Guglielmo Giannini in 1944 and constituted the first expression of populism in Italy's history. In the newspaper *L'Uomo qualunque*, Giannini juxtaposed the crowd (*folla*), that is, the peaceful and laborious multitude of productive individuals, to the tyrannical group of professional politicians (*uomini politici professionali*).

elements of Berlusconi's populist legacy persisted throughout these phases. Since Renzi and Meloni are sometimes classified as populists, and we are interested in whether a populist legacy can also extend beyond populist governments, we also include in our analysis more briefly the Monti and Letta governments (which preceded Renzi), the Gentiloni government (which followed it) and then the Conte II and Draghi governments (which preceded the Meloni government). Analysing this last group of governments allows us to increase the validity of our findings by assessing whether the legacy of populism also reached to decidedly non-populist, technocratic governments. A further reason to select the case of Italy for a plausibility probe is the fact that Italy, other than countries with long-term populist governments like Turkey or Hungary, did not experience strong democratic backsliding. Moreover, the rather long time period that has passed since the end of the Berlusconi era makes this a particularly challenging test case. Our analysis is based on a broad range of original-language primary sources, including speeches in the Italian parliament, newspaper reports, writings by the politicians analysed and expert interviews, as well as the secondary literature. We conclude by discussing alternative explanations for continuities in Italian foreign policy and by outlining avenues for further research on the legacy of populism.

I. State of the Art

The past few years saw the emergence of a burgeoning literature on the international dimensions of populism (for overviews of this growing field of research, see Cadier et al., 2025b; Wajner et al., 2024; Wajner and Giurlando, 2024). Several studies focused on how populism impacts foreign policy, addressing issues ranging from the preferences of populist parties (Verbeek and Zaslove, 2017) to populist governments' legitimation strategies and transnational connections (Wajner, 2022), their bilateral relationships with selected countries (e.g., Jakimów et al., 2025), their approaches to international institutions (Pacciardi et al., 2024; Söderbaum et al., 2021; Spandler and Söderbaum, 2023), to bilateral conflicts (Destradi and Plagemann, 2024), to international trade (Meislová and Chryssogelos, 2024) or to migration and defence policy (Ceccorulli et al., 2023). Other studies addressed the international implications of populist discourse (Cadier and Szulecki, 2020; Löfflmann, 2022; Wojczewski, 2020a, 2020b) or the impact of populist leaders' personalities (Fouquet, 2023; Özdamar and Ceydilek, 2020; Thiers and Wehner, 2022).

In this diverse literature, most studies focus on the short-term, more immediate impacts of populism on foreign policy, asking what is peculiar of populism and thus, more or less explicitly, in which ways populists' rise to power leads to changes. Single analyses take into account waves of populism, such as in Latin America (Wajner and Wehner, 2023), but do not explicitly emphasise the diachronic dimension of comparison. An exception are a few studies that address the consequences of the first Trump administration (Skonieczny and Sherel, 2024), looking at its legacy for US trade policy and at processes of 'foreign policy normalization' in its aftermath (Biegon and Hamdaoui, 2024). However, ultimately – and in contrast to the literature on the domestic political and economic consequences of populism – the long-term legacy of populism on foreign policy has so far remained unexplored (Wajner et al., 2024).

II. Theorising the Long-Term Effects of Populism on Foreign Policy

To develop expectations about the long-term effects of populism on foreign policy, we first need to define the key concepts we are working with. Following the ideational approach, we understand populism as a ‘thin-centered ideology’ that ‘considers society to be ultimately separated into two homogeneous and antagonistic groups, “the pure people” versus “the corrupt elite,” and [...] argues that politics should be an expression of the *volonté générale* (general will) of the people’ (Mudde, 2004, p. 543, emphasis removed). When it comes to our dependent variable, the ‘long-term’ impact of populism on foreign policy, we operationalise it as the continuation over time of policies initiated by populist governments. Instead of setting a fixed threshold measured in years to determine what ‘long-term’ means, we instead focus on changes in administrations or governments. We are thus interested in those influences of populism on foreign policy that persist after a populist leader has left office. If such effects remain in place for more than one following administration and are expected to continue in the future, we consider them to be long-term effects.

Our theorisation of the legacy of populism builds upon the literature on populism and foreign policy. Amongst its key findings is that populism is too ‘thin’ as an ideology to allow for clear predictions about foreign policy preferences: these are mostly driven by the ‘thick ideology’ that is combined with populism (Verbeek and Zaslove, 2017). However, most scholars agree that populists change the processes of foreign policy-making, that is, the way in which foreign policy is made, in important ways – and that these procedural shifts in turn have effects on foreign policy outcomes (Cadier et al., 2025a; Destradi and Plagemann, 2019). More specifically, populists in power re-shape foreign policy in two ways: they connect foreign policy more deeply to domestic politics as compared to their non-populist counterparts since they use it for domestic political mobilisation. By doing so, they politicise foreign policy (Cadier, 2024; Destradi et al., 2020). Moreover, they personalise and centralise decision-making (Wajner et al., 2024, p. 1823). It is precisely these two mechanisms that will leave a long-term imprint of populism on foreign policy.

Mobilisation/Politicisation

According to the literature on populism, in order to keep their legitimacy and credibility as anti-establishment figures, populists need to mobilise even after having come to power: they are constantly on the campaign trail (Müller, 2016; Urbinati, 2019). The literature on populism and foreign policy has revealed that foreign policy issues are often used for domestic political mobilisation (Destradi and Plagemann, 2019, p. 717; Jenne, 2021), and populists’ foreign policies are characterised by a ‘strong intermestic link [...] and the major importance of domestic considerations’ (Cadier et al., 2025a). This implies that populists are particularly prone to bringing foreign policy issues into the domestic political debate in order to mobilise support. In this way, foreign policy becomes ‘the continuation of domestic politics by other means’ (Cadier, 2024), and it becomes politicised. Since politicisation refers to the increasing contentiousness of decision-making, this very process leads to further diverging audience interests and to further mobilisation

(Schmitter, 1969, p. 166). In other words, mobilisation causes politicisation, and the latter, in turn, fuels additional mobilisation.

All this leads us to expect the populist mobilisation around foreign policy issues and the politicisation of foreign policy to have a long-term effect. We follow Zürn (2014, p. 50), who defines politicisation as ‘the act of transporting an issue into the field of politics – making previously unpolitical matters political’. The emerging literature on the populist politicisation of foreign policy has pointed to the central role of leaders, since ‘the main entrepreneurs of politicization are governing actors rather than non-governing ones’ (Cadier, 2024, p. 4; see also Destradi et al., 2022).

Research on the politicisation of European governance points at three interrelated dimensions of politicisation, which we expect to matter also in the long term: salience, polarisation and actor expansion (De Wilde et al., 2016). First of all, since populists use foreign policy issues to fight political opponents or end up ‘over-prioritizing domestic incentives and considerations over external ones’ (Cadier, 2024), foreign policy will not just become increasingly contested (Wiener, 2014), but also potentially more salient to the public. This is relevant in the long term, because once issues have become salient, they tend to remain so (Dennison, 2019). In the field of electoral studies (Dennison, 2019), empirical research on the politicisation of the European Union (EU) during national election campaigns has shown that, whilst there is not a uniform tendency towards more or less politicisation, there definitely is a persistence of the politicised issues.

Also, the polarisation dimension leads us to expect long-term effects. As Hutter and Kriesi (2019) show, the polarisation of issues such as European integration tended to persist over time, and computational models demonstrate that the self-reinforcing dynamics of polarisation are difficult to reverse (Macy et al., 2021). Similarly, we can expect the expansion of actors interested in foreign policy issues to contribute to a long-term impact of the politicisation of foreign policy. If politicisation means making previously unpolitical matters ‘political’ (Zürn, 2014), then it involves moving foreign policy out of just the purview of a narrow community of experts and ‘bringing’ it to the people by connecting it to domestic politics. As Cadier (2024) points out, this is what distinguishes populist from non-populist politicisation: whilst non-populist leaders might use diversionary wars to distract the public from domestic political developments, populist politicisation precisely aims ‘to re-focus attention on domestic politics’ (Cadier, 2024, p. 5) via international issues. Therefore, we expect populist mobilisation/politicisation of foreign policy issues to have long-term consequences via the increased salience, polarisation and the expansion of actors interested in foreign policy that emerges after populist leaders bring foreign policy issues into domestic political debates.

Personalisation/Centralisation

The second main feature of populist foreign policy-making is the personalisation of power. Whilst more personalised decision-making has become a broader trend in democratic countries’ foreign policies in recent years, as exemplified by the proliferation of leader-level summits, personalisation is particularly prevalent amongst populist leaders. This derives from populists’ understanding of democratic representation as a direct connection between the populist leader and the ‘people’. Some conceptualisations of populism like the strategic one go so far as to see this direct link as the main characteristic

of populism (Weyland, 2001). According to Urbinati (2019), this connection is so immediate that populists literally consider themselves the ‘embodiment’ of the popular will.

In foreign policy, this personalisation of power implies that leaders tend to concentrate decision-making in their hands, marginalising conventional foreign policy ‘elites’. These include advisors and experts, think tanks and most notably diplomats. Personalisation thus goes hand in hand with centralisation and with a range of reforms to foreign policy institutions. We have ample evidence of populist governments centralising foreign policy decision-making (Jumle et al., 2025), which becomes focused on the person of the populist leader and a small circle of advisors or, sometimes, personal friends. A weakening of foreign ministries is one frequent institutional manifestation of populism in power, but the restructuring of foreign policy institutions can take place in various ways, from closing entire agencies (as with USAID at the beginning of the second Trump administration) to reshuffling competencies amongst ministries or staffing foreign ministries with political appointees (Drezner, 2019; Huju, 2022; Lequesne, 2021).

These institutional changes introduced as a result of populist personalisation of decision-making are likely to have a long-lasting impact. The literature on path dependency shows that institutional processes are grounded in a dynamic of ‘increasing returns’ (Pierson, 2000). This makes institutions’ instability unproductive: ‘Once established, institutions thus reinforce the reproduction of legacies since already existing institutional patterns represent so-called sunk costs and are thus less expensive and more readily available than creating new ones’ (Leithner and Libby, 2017). An example of such longer term consequences of populist institutional reforms was Trump’s onslaught on the State Department (Drezner, 2019), with positions remaining vacant for a long time: ‘the Biden administration [acted] slowly to reverse the effects of the purge’ (Farrow, 2021). The creation of new departments or other modifications to existing structures also are likely to be durable. At the same time, institutions tend to resist change, and the legacy of populist personalisation/centralisation will vary depending on their resilience.

If a populist government significantly and consistently resorts to personalisation and centralisation in foreign policy-making, we expect the weakening of traditional foreign policy institutions to last in the longer term. In sum, we argue that populism will have an often under-estimated long-term effect. Whilst, on the one hand, populism in power may not change the fundamental tenets of a country’s foreign policy, on the other hand, its very mechanisms can lead to long-lasting modifications in foreign policy-making.

III. Berlusconi’s Foreign Policy

Italy’s foreign policy under Berlusconi did not fundamentally change in terms of its main strategic orientations and alliances. Nonetheless, four shifts took place. First, Berlusconi put relations with the United States at the top of his government’s priorities. Second, he explicitly affirmed the relevance of a partnership with Putin’s regime regardless of democratic concerns. Third, by showing little enthusiasm for the launch of the Euro on 1 January 2002, he sowed the seed of Euroscepticism amongst the Italian public, thus fostering demands for change in the EU. Fourth, Berlusconi went beyond the traditional Italian policy of supporting the Palestinian cause and adopted a more pro-Israeli stance after 9/11. In this way, he also established a connection between foreign and security policy, on one hand, and migration policy, on the other. Amongst the most important

changes to Italian foreign policy during the Berlusconi years were especially procedural elements, notably the mobilisation/politicisation of foreign policy as well as the personalisation/centralisation of decision-making.

Mobilisation/Politicisation: Bringing Foreign Policy to the People

Berlusconi used foreign policy for domestic mobilisation, and by doing so, he politicised international affairs. Like other populists, this meant bringing foreign policy to the people – in his case making use of his vast commercial television network. For example, he promoted the idea that he had been the facilitator of the true end of the Cold War via the NATO–Russia summit he hosted near Rome in 2002 – and to do so, he called the A team from his media network, Mediaset, ‘including quiz-show producers and variety-show designers’ (Friedman, 2015, p. 140) to produce a television show instructing Italians about this achievement. Mediatising foreign affairs was more than just an effort to increase domestic prestige. For Berlusconi, international developments had to be shown and explained to the Italian people. Thus, Russia’s rapprochement with NATO was presented as beneficial to Italian trade and economic growth. When inviting Putin to his private residence on 18 April 2008, immediately after winning the general election, Berlusconi emphasised the strengthening of economic interchange: ‘there are good possibilities of collaboration of Eni, Enel and other companies in joint projects’, he declared (in Signore, 2008).

Another way of bringing foreign policy into domestic political debates was the introduction of Law 11/2005 by Berlusconi’s government. This law requested the executive to report to the Parliament the positions it intended to take at meetings of the European Council. As we will discuss below, over time, government communications to Parliament have morphed into an occasion for politicising European and international issues.

Mobilisation and politicisation were particularly marked when it came to the 2003 war in Iraq and Berlusconi’s support for the War on Terror – even though, interestingly, Berlusconi in this case was not successful in generating support for his US-friendly policy, whilst certainly making foreign policy more salient to the Italian public and increasing polarisation around it. The Italian public was mostly sceptical of Italy’s military participation in the invasion of Iraq. On 18 March 2003, in the midst of preparations for war, a poll by the Pew Research Center (2003) indicated that the number of people with a favourable image of the United States had plummeted in Italy, from 70% one year earlier to only 34%. Having politicised the war eventually became a boomerang for Berlusconi, with the opposition ready to fan the flames of politicisation to get him in trouble and mass demonstrations ultimately turning into a protest against Berlusconi’s right-wing government (della Porta and Diani, 2003).

Yet, the most politicised foreign policy issue during the Berlusconi governments was the EU. At the core of Berlusconi’s politicisation of Italy’s role in the EU was not a wholesale rejection of European integration nor a threat to act against the EU, but rather a criticism of the modalities and features of co-operation in the EU, connected to criticism of his domestic political rivals. In the summer of 2002, Berlusconi argued against European constraints by claiming that there were two schools of thought: on the one hand, the conventional, ‘conservative’ approach shaped by his centre-left political rival and then-President of the European Commission, Romano Prodi, who, according to

Berlusconi, believed that it was enough to wait for economic recovery to happen. On the other hand, Berlusconi presented himself as the leading figure of a more advanced school, that of liberals, who wanted to boost investment through tax reductions but were constrained by the EU's deficit rules. Thus, Berlusconi used EU issues to mobilise domestic support by pitting his ideas against those of Prodi and presenting the EU as an obstacle to much-needed reforms. At the same time, he continued to support the notion of co-operation within the EU, arguing that these matters should be discussed with Italy's European allies: 'We will decide together' (Berlusconi, 2002a, p. 6). Unlike other anti-European populist leaders, Berlusconi did not propose to leave the EU but to pursue pro-Italian policies within it.

Whilst, other than most European populists, Berlusconi in his speeches in parliament and at political meetings did not criticise the Euro as such, he was vocally critical of the methods adopted for the introduction of the single currency. Also, he disagreed with EU policies about tax reduction and economic recovery and with EU governance. For example, in a speech at the Senate on 28 April 2005, Berlusconi blamed EU governance rules for sidelining national governments whilst not equipping the European Central Bank with the competencies to solve economic problems: 'It is a solution that does not depend on a national government; it is a solution that can concern the European Central Bank, which, having had the mission to control inflation, only does that' (Berlusconi, 2006, p. 92). More than this, Berlusconi even questioned the EU as a polity. His support of the expansion of the EU to include Putin's Russia (Mennitti, 2002) ignored the need to respect the Copenhagen criteria for EU membership. The basic idea was that Italy no longer benefited from EU membership and, therefore, had to change its European foreign policy (Telò, 2013). Overall, therefore, Berlusconi politicised Italy's role in the EU by introducing a peculiar Eurosceptic discourse and explicit criticism of EU governance that were unprecedented for an Italian prime minister and that resonated with the public.

Finally, Berlusconi's changed approach to Israel was also politicised. The emergence of anti-Islam rhetoric, along with increasing support for the cause of democratic Israel in the Middle East, capitalised on the fear of many Italians of the terrorist threat and the cultural challenge brought by Muslim migrants in Italy. Berlusconi thus interpreted Israel's battle against Palestinian terrorism 'as part of the fight that the "Western and democratic world" was conducting after September 11 to defend itself against the Islamist jihadist attack' (Marzano, 2011, p. 88), thus politicising this foreign-policy re-orientation. Meanwhile, he connected foreign policy to migration policy, securitising the latter and using it for domestic mobilisation. Ultimately, this also translated into an unprecedented policy of border externalisation, which was taken over by successive governments. For example, an informal bilateral agreement signed in July 2003 included the supply of specialised tools to help the Libyan authorities patrol the land and sea borders (Paoletti, 2010), and a Treaty on Friendship, Partnership and Cooperation was signed by Berlusconi and Libyan leader Gaddafi in 2008. This was presented as an achievement that reduced immigration to Italy by 90% within a year (Governo Berlusconi, 2010).

Personalisation/Centralisation: Reforming Foreign Policy for the People

Personalisation and centralisation of foreign policy-making were two intertwined processes that deeply characterised the years of Berlusconi's governments. First of all,

Berlusconi personalised foreign policy by personally playing a highly visible role in it and taking care of foreign policy matters.² This manifested, for example, in his personal ‘catering diplomacy’ (Andreatta and Brighi, 2004) whilst preparing international summits. During the G7 summit of Naples on 8–10 July 1994, Berlusconi introduced a new distinctive pattern to diplomatic praxis by emphasising personal relationships and behaving like a friendly and generous host (Diodato and Niglia, 2019, p. 57).

In 2002, Berlusconi combined the role of head of government with that of foreign minister for more than 8 months.³ Afterwards, he continued to engage in foreign policy by forging close personal relationships with many leaders, both during official summits and in unofficial meetings at his private residences. For example, Berlusconi organised a meeting between Bush and Putin in July 2001 following the G8 Summit, and exactly this meeting paved the way for Russia’s rapprochement with NATO (Diodato and Niglia, 2019, pp. 110–111). He chaired three G8 summits (1994, 2001 and 2009), trying to play a proactive role thanks to his chemistry with other leaders (Brighi, 2013, p. 129). Even after having left government, Berlusconi cultivated personal relationships with world leaders. For example, in 2014 during the Asia-Europe Meeting (ASEM) Summit organised by the Renzi government, Putin went to Berlusconi’s private residence after having discussed the Ukraine issue with Merkel (Ansa, 2014). The annexation of Crimea had taken place a few months earlier.

In his foreign policy decision-making processes, Berlusconi always relied on a small team of loyal experts. In international affairs, his principal adviser was Valentino Valentini, a former interpreter and polyglot, appointed Chief of the Prime Minister’s Office and Special Adviser on Foreign Relations in 2001. Within his circle of advisers, we find personal friends and collaborators from marketing to journalism. In 1996, whilst reorganising his party after his ouster from government, Berlusconi in typical populist fashion stated that Forza Italia was the first great post-ideological party whose choices would be in the hands of voters and elects rather than those of bureaucrats, officials or professional politicians (Poli, 2001, p. 116). The impact of junior coalition partners was relevant for specific issues (Verbeek and Zaslove, 2015), but they did not compromise Berlusconi’s ability to personify government action.

Two distinct but related processes fostered the nexus between personalisation and centralisation: first, an increased role of Palazzo Chigi (the seat of the government) in foreign policy-making; second, a policy of public administration reforms, which included the functioning of the Farnesina (the seat of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs).

The first serious attempt to promote centralisation via institutional reforms came as early as in 1994, with Berlusconi nominating a Minister for Italians in the World, and creating a corresponding department at Palazzo Chigi. After his successor Romano Prodi moved this department to the Foreign Ministry, Berlusconi re-incorporated it into the

²The Italian Constitution does not fully regulate the exercise of foreign power. The Government manages foreign policy, from negotiating and signing international treaties to military interventions abroad. However, there is a triangulation with the Parliament, which has a supervisory function over the government’s activities, and also with the President of the Republic (head of state), who has command of the armed forces, chairmanship of the Supreme Defense Council (an institutional body through which he or she acquires information on the government’s security orientations) and specific competence as guarantee of international treaties and Italy’s membership in international organisations.

³Berlusconi’s interim at the Farnesina lasted until November 2002, when Frattini, a loyalist with a strong reputation as expert of the public administration, was appointed as his successor. Frattini was Minister of Foreign Affairs from 2002 to 2004 and from 2008 to 2011.

prime minister's office in 2001, making sure that it would receive timely information on strategies, programmes and international visits planned by the Farnesina (Luci, 2023). Amongst the various activities of the new ministry were the organisation of the 'First International Conference of Italian Entrepreneurs in the World' (20–22 October 2003) and the establishment of a 'Confederation of Italian Entrepreneurs in the World' (21 June 2004). Besides centralising a relevant function of foreign policy at Palazzo Chigi, the activities of this department also reflected Berlusconi's understanding of foreign policy as an entrepreneurial tool for promoting Italy and making the country more competitive. In his speech to the Chamber of Deputies to announce his interim Foreign Minister, Berlusconi said: 'The interim position at Farnesina will last for the time strictly necessary to make the most of our ancient and wise diplomatic network, taking advantage of the elements of reform and innovation that are necessary today [...]. Someone has made irony about the *made in Italy* and about diplomats forced to act as commercial agents. Irony is always a good thing, but I think it is really out of place here: it is a sign of short-sightedness, distraction or, worse, ignorance and prejudice' (Berlusconi, 2002b, p. 95).

This new approach epitomises Berlusconi's scepticism of traditional diplomacy. This reflected his broader contempt for the Italian public administration, whose image had generally been tainted in post-Cold War Italy. Here, Berlusconi's reforms were part of a broader trend. When Berlusconi was in opposition between 1996 and 2001, the centre-left governments implemented several public administration reforms, including the creation of new directorates in the Foreign Ministry in January 2000 to overcome old distinctions between politics and economics (Vattani, 2000). It is difficult to assess how much Berlusconi's previous efforts towards centralisation and reform influenced such changes even from the opposition. In any case, once back in office, Berlusconi implemented the reform, and he did so by further centralising foreign policy decision-making.

During the third Berlusconi government in 2010, a new reform of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs brought further changes: a reduction in the number of directorates from 13 to eight, divided no longer by geographical areas but by themes coinciding with strategic priorities; the establishment of a stable and structured relationship between Farnesina and the Ministry of Economy; the assignment of diplomatic advisors (coming from the diplomatic career) to each ministry of the government; and the creation of the figure of ambassadorial managers, who should be called upon to manage the budgets of the foreign offices in an increasingly autonomous and entrepreneurial way (Matarazzo, 2010). Whilst similar reforms had also been accomplished in Spain, France, Germany and the United Kingdom, for Berlusconi, this was also a way to ease the burden of bureaucracy and foster a business-oriented foreign policy.

The reforms in the Ministry of Foreign Affairs went hand in hand with the centralisation of international affairs at Palazzo Chigi, including on security issues. In the 2000s, the emerging threats from international terrorism impacted the distribution of competencies amongst different ministries. Palazzo Chigi became the reference point for addressing the new security challenge, thus limiting the competencies of the Foreign Ministry and, to some extent, those of the Defense Ministry and the Interior Ministry. One important reform was that of intelligence services. Throughout both the Cold War and the 1990s, in Italy, the intelligence apparatus had been seen with scepticism, as a deep state potentially endangering democratic values. In June 2002, Berlusconi submitted a reform

bill titled ‘Amendments to Law No. 801 of October 24, 1977’, which was a first attempt to foster a new ‘culture of intelligence’ after 9/11. It included, amongst other things, intelligence co-ordination by Palazzo Chigi (Senato, 2002), and it was adopted as Law n. 124 in 2007, after Berlusconi returned to the opposition.

More in general, Berlusconi always defended his centralisation of power, including in parliamentary debates and relations with the Quirinale (seat of the President of the Republic), where he emphasised the necessity of Palazzo Chigi adopting a ‘presidential style’ of government (Calise, 2005), despite acting in a parliamentary system with separation of duties between head of state and head of government.

IV. Berlusconi’s Legacy

After having outlined how Berlusconi resorted to foreign policy issues for domestic mobilisation and how he personalised and centralised foreign policy-making, we now proceed to carry out a plausibility probe of our expectations concerning the longer term legacy of populism, focusing on the three above-mentioned phases of the post-Berlusconi era.

Mobilisation and the Longer Term Politicisation of Foreign Policy in Italy

In the literature on foreign policy, there is an agreement that globalisation has made foreign policy issues more relevant to domestic publics all over the world and that politics does not ‘stop at the water’s edge’. Here, we aim to perform a first assessment of whether the mobilisation and politicisation introduced during the Berlusconi era remained in place under following governments. In a nutshell, we find that this was indeed the case, even though we do not find clear indications that this automatically translated into an increased salience of foreign policy to the Italian public.⁴

As we mentioned above, under Berlusconi, Law 15/2005 was introduced requiring the Italian government to inform the Parliament about foreign policy developments. The technocratic Monti government (2011–2013) amended this law with the 234/2012 to make government communications before the chambers of parliament mandatory, and the short-lived Letta government (2013–2014) conformed to the new law’s requirements, with the prime minister giving detailed and rather unimaginative accounts of foreign policy to the Italian parliament. When Renzi came to power, he gave those reports a new spirit and tone: instead of listing foreign policy developments, Renzi used those reports to showcase his government’s foreign policy achievements, providing vivid accounts of his meetings with decision-makers in Africa, Asia or elsewhere. Ahead of Italy’s Presidency of the Council of the EU in 2014, Renzi emphatically argued in favour of European integration in what was an obviously political speech addressing the opposition and the Italian public, rather than a mere report of his government’s activities:

We go to Europe when we leave the house in the morning, we go to Europe when we walk through the streets of our cities [...]. This is Europe, it’s not something other than us. And maybe we should start by saying with greater determination not what Europe

⁴Eurobarometer data do not indicate a significant increase in the salience of international issues over time in Italy. The overall visibility of foreign news broadcast on national evening news is not particularly high in Italy, but it grew over time. From 2012 to 2017, it was 19% (Osservatorio 2017), and it rose to over 36% (Osservatorio 2024).

must tell us or give us, but what we are giving to Europe and are asking from it. Europe is not a set of requirements that we approach with worry [...]. Europe is what we will be able to build, Europe will be what we will be able to build. (Camera dei Deputati, 2014)

Seeking legitimacy for his government ahead of Italy's presidency of the European semester, Renzi thus continued to bring foreign policy issues into political debates, trying to increase the relevance of foreign policy issues by emphasising the importance of their European dimension. He also connected foreign policy with domestic politics by emphasising that his domestic reforms were necessary to improve Italy's standing in Europe. Meanwhile, he 'engaged in the frequent use of strident [...] rhetorical attacks on the EU on the austerity issue' (Coticchia and Davidson, 2016, p. 60). Alternating – in a way similar to Berlusconi – between combative and positive positions with respect to the EU, Renzi continued to politicise government decisions.

Whilst some scholars consider Renzi a populist, this is certainly not true of his predecessor Letta. Taking a counterfactual approach, we should find a different kind of communication before the parliament on the part of a non-populist government. Instead, in his second speech on 25 June 2013, Letta addressed the chamber as follows:

That is why we could not accept that the June European Council was only about procedures, governance, technicalities. That is why we wanted it to discuss real problems, issues that enter every day, every night, in the lives of all Italian and European families. [...] Now, we ask and want an extra effort: no assertions of principle, but immediate decisions that restore a sense of urgency on this issue, European and national operational tools, resources, stringent timing that focuses intervention on a short time horizon to achieve maximum impact right away. (Camera dei Deputati, 2013, pp. 3–4)

In these words, we again find a political appeal, and the same urgency displayed by Berlusconi to seek quick solutions to international problems rather than relying on the timing of institutional diplomacy.

During the 'populist decade', the elements of mobilisation and politicisation equally remained in place. They became particularly visible during the all-populist 'yellow-green' coalition government formed by the Five Star Movement (M5S) and the Lega with Giuseppe Conte as prime minister. During this 'Conte I' government, we saw parallel mobilisation efforts around foreign policy by the two parties on distinct issues. Notably, the two vice-prime ministers, Luigi Di Maio (M5S) and Matteo Salvini (Lega), both resorted to foreign policy issues to increase their profile within the coalition and to cater to their distinct constituencies. This was most visible in Salvini's approach to migration, which he pursued as Minister of the Interior adopting policies like the closure of ports to ships carrying immigrants, in violation of international law and in open opposition to other European governments. These foreign policies were clearly related to domestic politics as epitomised by the Trump-like slogan 'Italians first'. Notably, however, the yellow-green government took over elements of migration policies that had already been introduced by previous governments, such as the inclusion of the Mare Nostrum mission into Frontex under Renzi, or the signing of a memorandum with the Libyan government in 2017 under the preceding (non-populist) Gentiloni government. And several of those aspects, in turn, can be traced back to Berlusconi's border externalisation with Libya and to his rhetoric focused around the notion of helping migrants 'a casa loro' (at their

own home). Yet, Salvini used these policies in a much more aggressive way to generate domestic support. Possibly also to increase his profile within the coalition,⁵ Di Maio, who was the Minister of Economic Development, Labour and Social Policies and the second vice prime minister, equally used foreign policy for mobilisation. The most evident example was his mobilisation against France. Amongst other incidents, Di Maio accused France of ‘colonialism’ and travelled to Paris in February 2019 to meet members of the French ‘yellow vests’ protest movement, who had even called for overthrowing Macron’s government via a military coup (Darnis, 2019). Ultimately, ‘[t]he European foreign policy of the first Conte government can be labeled as a strategy of opposition’ (Cladi and Locatelli, 2021, p. 466). Attacking France was useful for mobilisation given a diffuse antipathy towards France amongst sections of the Italian population.⁶

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic that hit Italy very hard complicates a counterfactual discussion of the Conte II government, but some of the traits of Berlusconi’s legacy in terms of mobilisation remained in place. The prime minister played a key role in the new government’s international actions. Conte projected himself as an indispensable deal-maker in Europe by choosing to support Ursula von Der Leyen as the new President of the European Commission in 2019, and he tried to capitalise on this move to gain greater domestic support. Further, given the massive support provided to Italy via the NextGeneration EU post-pandemic recovery package, anti-EU mobilisation did not make much sense, and indeed, Italian public opinion matured a markedly more favourable attitude towards the EU (Pirozzi, 2021). Thus, Conte put more emphasis on presenting himself to the domestic public as the capable leader who brought such blessing to Italy.

The right-wing government led by Giorgia Meloni also used foreign policy for domestic political mobilisation. Unusually as compared to other Italian governments, foreign policy issues were the first point mentioned in the official programme of Meloni’s party (Fratelli d’Italia, 2022). Moreover, Meloni used her numerous international visits to showcase her government’s international engagement, up to the point that foreign policy is considered by Italian voters the area in which she has been most successful (Politico, 2023). Yet, mobilisation varied across different issues. On migration, Meloni’s policies ultimately displayed continuity with those of previous governments, albeit without reaching extreme manifestations like Salvini’s blockade of harbours. Yet, Meloni had strongly politicised migration, repeatedly attacking previous governments for having failed to engage with Africa and to develop a Mediterranean policy preventing migratory flows (Fratelli d’Italia, 2022). As a result, the Meloni government proposed the ‘Piano Mattei’ aimed at eradicating the causes of immigration, combating the spread of Islamist radicalism in sub-Saharan Africa, and ‘recover[ing], after years in which we preferred to retreat, our strategic role in the Mediterranean’ (Meloni, 2022). Ultimately, Meloni’s main argument on migration revolved around the notion that closer ties with Africa were needed in order to externalise border controls – a discourse in the Berlusconi-era tradition of using humanitarian justifications and resorting to development aid to prevent migration. By contrast, Meloni’s decisive support for Ukraine was not used to mobilise support to the same extent as it failed to meet the expectations of her right-wing base. As has been

⁵Interview with Italian scholar, Florence, 12 September 2022; telephone interview with retired Italian diplomat, 22 September 2022.

⁶Interviews with Italian academic, online, 19 September 2022; with Italian journalist, online, 20 September 2022.

noted, however, the Russian attack on Ukraine had the effect of temporarily suspending geopolitical polarisation in Italy (Bordignon et al., 2022).

When it comes to the politicisation of foreign policy, we thus see that the tendency to connect foreign policy issues with domestic political debates, which was initiated during the Berlusconi era, remained as an element of his populist legacy. The government's reports to parliament became a way for successive governments to gain support for their foreign policy initiatives, using the parliament as a sort of echo chamber to promote their approach. Moreover, especially on issues like EU-scepticism and migration, there was considerable continuity when it comes to governments using this topic to mobilise support (Monteleone, 2021). Yet, despite all these efforts, the salience of foreign policy to the Italian public did not clearly increase, and actor expansion primarily regarded political entrepreneurs, as when both Salvini and Di Maio tried to employ its mobilisation potential.

Personalisation and Centralisation as Longer Term Trends in Italian Foreign Policy

There are several indications that the personalisation and centralisation of foreign policy-making introduced during the populist Berlusconi era were elements that left a long-term legacy in Italian foreign policy. Overall, a greater centralisation of decision-making at Palazzo Chigi as well as the greater business orientation of foreign policy is an element of continuity that has been observed by several scholars (Diodato and Marchetti, 2023; Longo, 2011; Siddi, 2019).

The Renzi government displayed both personalisation and centralisation elements. For one, Renzi himself took centre stage on foreign policy issues with a number of highly visible international visits and an emphasis on personal relationships with world leaders such as the Saudi state minister Prince Mohammed bin Salman or the prime minister of Japan Shinzo Abe. Moreover, Renzi was generally favourable to the notion of strengthening the figure of the Italian prime minister – a decades-long debate around the concept of 'premierato' that can equally be traced back to the entirely new emphasis put on the role of the prime minister during the Berlusconi era. In terms of Renzi's relationship with the foreign policy bureaucracy, a major irritant was his nomination of business executive and Deputy Minister of Economic Development Carlo Calenda as Italy's Permanent Representative to the EU, a post that up to that moment had always been filled by diplomats and not by political appointees. The Farnesina, which had a long tradition of successfully resisting its own marginalisation, protested with vehemence. Flirting in general with both populist and technocratic arguments that discredited traditional party-based democracy, in matters of foreign policy Renzi managed to harmonise public orientations and his leadership: 'All of this is arrived at through a considerable degree of centralisation, including in the process of selection and articulation of goals, and presented as a pragmatic if not technical solution to problems, rather than an ideological stance' (Brighi and Giugni, 2016, p. 23).

Notably, personalisation continued even under the two governments led by independent technocrats in the post-Berlusconi era, Monti's technocratic government and Draghi's government of national unity. Whilst both leaders were certainly not prone to mobilise the people, their propensity to personalise and centralise foreign policy was evident. On 17 November 2011, after Monti's first speech before the Parliament, the

Financial Times headlined its commentary: ‘The man who could save Italy’. When Monti met Obama the following February, *Time* magazine relaunched the issue with a cover story titled: ‘Can this man save Europe?’ Monti himself also emphasised his personal ability to restore Italy’s credibility (Time, 2012). In Draghi’s case, we witnessed a similar process of putting the leader centre stage but influenced by the continuing health emergency and the energy supply crisis due to Italy’s dependence on Russia.

During the populist decade, the yellow-green government stands out for a specific pattern of double personalisation around the two vice-prime ministers and party leaders, Di Maio and Salvini, instead of around the figure of the prime minister. Whilst Salvini, who also served as minister of internal affairs, stressed the migration agenda, Di Maio, who also served as minister of economic development, insisted on the expansion of Italian trade and of inbound foreign direct investment. As both tried to increase their profile via foreign policy issues, Di Maio not only stands out for the above-mentioned irritations with France. He was also the driving force in the major foreign policy change of that government: the signing in March 2029 of a memorandum of understanding (MoU) with China to bring Italy into the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). Although the MoU was not rejected by the foreign policy bureaucracy, it is worth emphasising that Di Maio was personally invested into the agreement and presented it as his personal achievement. Moreover, assisted by Under-Secretary Michele Geraci, an academic who taught business and economics in foreign universities based in China, Di Maio ‘took control of the China dossier’ (Pugliese et al., 2022, p. 1039). The following November, Di Maio attended the China International Import Expo in Shanghai with Italy in the role of guest of honour country. A few days later, M5S veteran leader Beppe Grillo visited the Chinese embassy in an unusual and mysterious meeting. Further, in institutional terms, Di Maio centralised foreign policy decision-making in his own hands by taking the oversight of international trade away from the ministry of economic development to the ministry of foreign affairs when he became chief of this department in the Conte II government, a position he retained during the Draghi administration. Notably, Berlusconi himself had tried to make this move in 2002 but had failed due to the resistance of the minister of economic development at the time, Antonio Marzano (Pelosi, 2019).

When it comes to Meloni, elements of personalisation were also clearly visible during her first years in office – images like her selfie with Indian Prime Minister Modi put her personally centre stage, whilst at the same time conveying the message that, after not having renewed the BRI in December 2023, she was now firmly placing Italy in the ‘Indo-Pacific’ together with the United States and other Western allies (Carrer, 2024). The move away from China, in addition to support for Ukraine alongside the United States, shows how Italy’s anchorage to NATO is not contested and, indeed, that foreign policy remains consistent and aligned with traditional interests. Nonetheless, diplomatic practices have changed. For example, in terms of institutional reforms, Meloni transferred competencies for development co-operation from the Farnesina to Palazzo Chigi via her Piano Mattei: according to Law 2/2024, the Mattei Plan Steering Committee at Palazzo Chigi is responsible to co-ordinate Italy’s relations with African Nations, providing an annual report to Parliament. This means that the African and development co-operation dossier is now centralised at Palazzo Chigi. Finally, Meloni’s government is working on a reform to further centralise the intelligence agencies (Valentini, 2023).

The personalisation and centralisation of foreign policy in Italy, initially set in motion during the Berlusconi era, have become enduring trends that continue to shape the country's international engagements. This confirms the persistence of a new way of conducting foreign policy within a process of path dependence. Under Renzi, these trends were further emphasised. The populist yellow-green government, characterised by dual personalisation under Di Maio and Salvini, continued this pattern. Giorgia Meloni's tenure has also shown elements of personalisation and centralisation. More than this, even non-populist, technocratic leaders like Monti and Draghi retained this feature of foreign policy-making.

Conclusion

In this contribution, we made a first effort towards theorising the possible longer term consequences of populism in power. Our empirical analysis of the Italian case confirmed our expectations. The Berlusconi era, during which foreign policy was increasingly 'brought to the people' and therefore politicised, and during which a growing personalisation and centralisation of foreign policy-making took place, left a deep imprint onto Italian foreign policy. Successive governments maintained several key elements of such populist legacy, from the primacy of leader-level politics to the use of the government's report to parliament to politicise foreign policy issues, to a series of efforts at weakening the foreign ministry via institutional reforms and centralising competencies in the hands of the prime minister. Importantly, this populist legacy affected both populist and non-populist governments during the following two decades.

Two possible alternative explanations must be considered: (1) over time, also the emulation of other populist leaders around the world – instead of Berlusconi – could explain mobilisation and politicisation; (2) across many countries, governments have strengthened their role towards the parliaments, and foreign policy has become more strongly a domain of leader-level politics – thus, this might be a more general trend. Concerning emulation, we observed that international issues are not always successfully politicised, as for the Iraq war in 2003, or might not be politicised at all, as in the case of the Russia–Ukraine war in 2022, as they were not salient to the Italian public *per se* but retained potential for mobilisation. This potential to 'bring foreign issues to the people' appears to be a long-lasting effect and not one that emerges by emulating other international leaders. Especially the Russia–Ukraine war, which triggered high levels of mobilisation on the part of populists in other European countries and beyond, reveals that emulation is not necessarily a suitable alternative explanation. Concerning the more general trend towards a predominance of the executive and personalisation of foreign policy-making, only by comparing our findings with different case-studies could we confirm the link between path dependency in foreign policy-making and populist leaders. Future research should address, for example, the link between the duration in power of populist governments and the continuation of personalisation and centralisation in decision-making. Cases where a populist leader served for just one term, such as the Philippines under Duterte (Arugay et al., 2024), reveal that institutional changes can be more easily reverted, thus corroborating our assessment that populism has a distinct impact.

At any rate, this first plausibility probe of the Italian case shows that the impact of populism on foreign policy can be longer lasting and can persist even after populist

governments leave office. Future research will need to find out whether this is a broader trend and if our expectations would find confirmation in other cases as well. Moreover, other insights into the specific dynamics of these cases are needed in order to find out if there are deeper mechanisms at play beyond just institutional inertia. For example, populism might re-shape what the public expects from elected politicians, re-shaping patterns of communication about foreign policy issues and thereby forcing subsequent governments to continue along a similar path of politicisation and centralisation of foreign policy. All this would speak to a broader emerging strand of research that deals with the more indirect effects of populism on political culture.

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